

Effects of different drying methods on textural properties of nanocellulose aerogels

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SUMMARY

There is increasing research interest in nanocellulose aerogels because they have low density, hierarchical structure and they are biodegradable and biocompatible. Typically, aerogels are made by supercritical drying, freeze drying and vacuum drying. This work will report the effects that different drying methods have on textural properties of aerogels.

Keywords: Nanocellulose aerogel, supercritical drying, freeze drying, hierarchical structures, mechanical properties

Fabrication of nanocellulose aerogels

Nanocellulose fibrils are obtained from pulp after homogenization at high pressure [1]. Aerogel which is referred to as “solid smoke” is the lightest solid material in the world. Combines the advantages of cellulose and aerogel, nanocellulose aerogels have promising properties like sustainability, biocompatibility, low density, hierarchical porous structure. They have potential applications in nanocomposite as substrates or templates. Effects of freeze drying, vacuum drying and supercritical drying on porous structure and mechanical properties of aerogels will be reported.

Drying methods

Freeze drying, vacuum drying and supercritical drying are used to remove water from aqueous gel to prepare aerogel. In freeze drying, the aqueous gel was frozen by liquid N₂ and then kept in the vacuum oven for drying. In vacuum drying, the sample was dried by sublimation directly by vacuum. [2] In supercritical drying, water in aqueous gel was exchanged to ethanol first, and then the sample was transferred in a supercritical dryer with CO₂ as co-solvent.

Characterization of aerogels

JEOL JSM-7500 field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) was applied to characterize the structure in aerogels. Dynamic mechanical analysis was done by TA Instruments Q800. N₂ adsorption was used to measure surface area and porous properties.

Results and discussion

Hierarchical structure of aerogels from vacuum drying is shown in Fig 1. The resulting aerogel has density of 0.01-0.03 g /cm³. BET surface area of aerogels is higher from freeze drying than from vacuum drying as shown in table 1. It is said that supercritical drying works better than freeze drying, more work will be carried out as soon as possible in supercritical drying for comparison.

Figure 1 Structure of nanocellulose aerogel from vacuum drying by FE- SEM characterization

Table 1 Properties of aerogels from different drying methods [2]

Drying method	BET surface	Pore size
Freeze drying	66 m ² / g	2% micro-, 98% meso
Vacuum drying	20	1% micro-, 94% meso, 5% macro

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